

A case study on evaluating the alignment of internship education with its objectives in the civil aviation departments of vocational high schools

Murat Durali^{1*}

¹Ministry of National Education, muratdurali@anadolu.edu.tr

²Eskişehir Technical University, denizturkmen@eskisehir.edu.tr

Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <p>Keywords: Internship in Civil Aviation Vocational High School Case Study Ground Service Vocational Education</p> <p>Received: 6 November 2024 Revised: 24 December 2024 Accepted: 26 December 2024</p>	<p>This study conducted a case study to evaluate the suitability of internship education provided in the civil aviation departments of vocational high schools. The primary objective of the research is to identify the challenges faced by vocational high school students during their internship and the factors contributing to these challenges. Additionally, the study investigates how the experiences gained during the internship reflect on the students' professional competencies. The research was carried out within the framework of a qualitative research design, using in-depth interviews as the data collection tool. The participants of the study consisted of vocational high school students enrolled in the civil aviation department. The findings of the study indicate that intern students struggled to effectively apply the theoretical knowledge gained during their coursework in the internship environment. Furthermore, deficiencies in equipment and training within the companies where internships were conducted made it difficult for students to achieve the expected outcomes of their internships. In this context, the study emphasizes the need for improving the practical training environments in companies and enhancing the qualifications of educators to ensure the internship education fully meets its objectives.</p>

1. Introduction

Rapid technological developments affecting all sectors have a significant impact on the aviation sector. With the contribution of globalization, the aviation sector is expanding and the need for professional human resources working in this field is increasing. In addition, the aviation sector is a field that requires high safety and security awareness. For this reason, it is also important to train qualified human resources to master the field. Internship trainings can provide operational awareness to students who are trained in this field before their professional career. In the aviation sector, where competition is intensifying, there is a need for individuals who can make quick decisions, think conceptually and at the same time deal with the activities at the operational level. In order to meet this human need in the field of Civil Aviation, it is aimed to train educated and competent individuals (Numanoğlu et al., 2018).

*Corresponding author. Murat Durali.

Cite this article: Durali, M. & Türkmen, D. (2024). A case study on evaluating the alignment of internship education with its objectives in the civil aviation departments of vocational high schools. *Research in Aviation Management*, 4(2), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14563435>

The field of civil aviation ground handling services has been opened in vocational high schools in Turkey within the scope of vocational education before undergraduate education; and since 2015, education in this field has been provided at secondary level.

This research focuses on the difficulties and experiences of the students of the newly opened civil aviation department in terms of internship. Although education has been provided at the undergraduate level for many years, the newness of this department at the secondary education level has brought some difficulties in the internship process.

Although the internship process provides certain conveniences for high school students, there are also some problems. For example, there are many problems such as low recognition in the sector, graduates not being able to find a job in the sector, insufficient foreign language education, difficulties in finding an internship place, and incomplete curriculum (Somuncu, 2019). Therefore, this study provides an opportunity for a more detailed study on internship experiences and solution suggestions from a pedagogical perspective.

In this study, it is aimed to analyze and describe the gains of civil aviation students through their experiences in the internship process. In this context, the following questions were sought to be answered:

1. How do civil aviation students describe the theoretical courses they took in school and the skills and experiences they gained during the internship process?
2. How did the internship process affect students' professional competence?
3. How do the vocational courses given in high school contribute to the internship process?

2. Literature Review

Internships in the civil aviation sector help students and new graduates improve their professional skills, gain work experience, expand their sectoral networks and determine their career goals. The aviation sector is a sector where theoretical knowledge must be transformed into practice. Therefore, interns can improve their professional skills by gaining hands-on experience. However, it is seen in the literature that there are also problems experienced during the internship process.

When the literature on the internship process is examined, firstly the problems encountered in the field of civil aviation and then the internship problems encountered in secondary education in general are found.

Yavaş et al. (2021) evaluated the internship experiences of aviation students under the headings of “personal evaluation, internship experience, working environment and relationship with the university”. In general, it was found that the internship satisfaction levels of the intern students were high, but it was stated that the theoretical knowledge they received in higher education institutions was insufficient during the internship phase. Therefore, it was stated that an update in the course content of the programs providing aviation education could eliminate this inadequacy. Taking into account the wishes of the sector will be beneficial at this point.

Somuncu (2019) stated that the newly created Civil Aviation department in secondary education has some infrastructure deficiencies. Accordingly, he stated that the lack of course materials should be eliminated, more financing should be allocated, and better planning should be done for the department. He also stated that this department, which was opened in some provinces, has employment problems for graduates due to the lack of airports in the region.

Chen et al. (2021) found that students who are able to fully grasp the ethics of getting along well at work reach the ultimate value of personal growth in this process. The perception of success was shown to mean that students felt a sense of joy and accomplishment after the internship was over. Students are filled with satisfaction, especially when they receive compliments from their supervisors or passengers. These students were very happy with their choice to stay in the aviation industry after graduation.

Leslie and Richardson (2000) stated that students have high expectations from internships, but the course contents and internships do not match.

Regarding internship problems in secondary education, Çiçek (2021) reported that some students were underestimated by the staff and were expected to do much more than they should. This caused students to feel under pressure. Therefore, companies that accept intern students should be made aware of this issue and other employees should be informed about how they should approach interns. In addition, teachers acting as coordinators said that they should ask their students various questions that could reveal problems related to their internships. The reason is that some students think that some negative situations do not constitute a problem during their vocational training, or they see these situations as a natural flow of business life.

Örnek (2021) stated in his research that transportation services logistics branch students encountered some negativity during the internship process. Therefore, it was seen that there were changes in the satisfaction levels of the students, and the reasons for this were; the wage received during the sector internship, not enough in-service training provided by the enterprise, not working in areas suitable for the department studied, doing a different job outside of their professional field, and the managers of the enterprise not treating the employees fairly, whether they are interns or not. It was stated that internship places can mostly be found by the school administration. In addition, since the working areas in the logistics sector are predominantly in the private sector, providing employment to students after internship indicates that it will increase satisfaction.

Özgül (1995), in his research on the vocational effects of the places where vocational high school students do their internships, found that the majority of graduates work outside their own fields. While changing the field of vocational high school graduates is an important loss for the national economy due to the high cost of vocational education, it is also an important loss because the vocational knowledge gained in enterprises is not utilized. For this reason, multifaceted efforts should be made to ensure that the majority of vocational education graduates work in their own field. According to the results of Karataş's (2017) research on the problems of vocational and technical Anatolian high school students doing internship in enterprises, students: Not taking internship insurance into account in retirement, having an end-of-year skills exam, low internship wage, long working hours, and not being able to spare time for their families.

Yılmaz (2021) obtained similar results to other studies when he looked at the suitability of the education given in the accounting departments of vocational high schools to market needs. Accordingly, he concluded that the theoretical education for vocational knowledge and skills given to students is sufficient, but there is not enough practical training to meet the needs of the sector. Although there are departmental differences, internship problems in secondary education have common aspects.

Arslan (2020) found common problems with other fields in the evaluation of vocational high school information technologies field internships: It was revealed that the students did not know and use their rights given to them by the relevant laws and regulations during the internship. It was determined that intern students had the most difficulty in getting permission, were rarely used for errands such as cleaning, tea and carrying goods, etc., could not benefit from lunch at the workplace, could not meet regularly with the coordinator teacher at the workplace, and were verbally insulted at the workplace. Problems such as these cause demotivation, reluctance or low performance in intern students.

Sarı (2007) emphasizes that the education given in vocational and technical schools should be oriented towards practice. He expressed the importance of ensuring school-sector cooperation. He stated that students cannot find the opportunity to apply the knowledge and skills they learn at school in the enterprises where they do internship. It has been revealed that this occurs more in some departments.

Pınarlık et al. (2022) emphasized the need for improvements in the content of courses offered in the aircraft technology program. Additionally, they highlighted that placing greater emphasis on foreign language education would align better with the expectations of internship workplaces.

Wang et al. (2019) identified the factors influencing students' internships as planning, guidance, establishing proper connections with the industry, improving the learning environment, expanding the scope of practical applications, innovating application methods, and protecting students' rights and interests.

Demirci (2007) found that students were insufficiently aware of and unable to fully utilize their rights granted by relevant laws and regulations during their skill training in businesses. To address this, students should be informed about the operations, rules, and workplace culture of their internship sites before starting their internships. Furthermore, it was observed that students interning at firms three days a week became distanced

from the school environment and their classes. Demirci emphasized the need to implement necessary measures to prevent a decline in students' interest in their academic studies.

Gülsoy (2007), in his research on the internship practices of vocational high school students, emphasized that coordinating teachers should be assigned to oversee internships in their own subject areas as much as possible. Otherwise, it has been observed that coordinating teachers may not be able to provide sufficient guidance to their students. He also underlined the need to create opportunities in workplaces that enable students to acquire the knowledge and skills necessary during their training period. Additionally, Gülsoy highlighted the importance of ensuring that students complete their internships with realistic perspectives on working life, thereby preventing potential issues that could negatively impact their future careers.

Students with internship experience have been found to face fewer challenges in making decisions about their careers. Moreover, it has been observed that students who did not make their program choices consciously tend to participate in internships with reluctance (Konate, 2022). Pala (2016) stated that vocational high school students often work in areas unrelated to their fields and that interns are perceived as a source of cheap labor.

According to the findings of Karataş (2017) in his research on the problems faced by vocational and technical Anatolian high school students during their internships, students identified several issues: the exclusion of internship insurance from retirement considerations, the existence of a year-end skill examination, the inadequacy of internship wages, long working hours, and the inability to allocate time for their families.

The practical implementation of skill and internship training by vocational and technical education students in businesses provides significant benefits, as it allows them to learn the tasks in their natural working environment (Numanoğlu et al., 2018).

To highlight the importance of internships in vocational high schools, the reports of MEB (2014) provide valuable insights. The 2014-2018 strategic document and action plan include a SWOT analysis. According to this analysis, the presence of a culture supporting internships and vocational training in businesses is identified as a strength. However, the insufficient quality of vocational training and internships in businesses is noted as a weakness. Additionally, the lack of active engagement by businesses in workplace training and internships is identified as a threat.

MEB (2019), includes a SWOT analysis for vocational and technical high schools in its 2019-2023 strategic plan. According to this analysis, the existence of a system that allows for the recognition of prior learning in vocational and technical education is identified as a strength. However, the lack of an assessment and evaluation system in vocational and technical education aligned with modular training (learning outcomes) is seen as a weakness. Opportunities include the private sector's openness to collaboration in vocational and technical education, its support for strengthening the technological infrastructure of educational environments, and the perception that vocational and technical education is essential for training a qualified workforce. On the other hand, the negative perception of vocational and technical education, along with the rapid pace of technological change and the uncertainty regarding the future of vocational and technical education in an increasingly digitalized world, are identified as threats.

In conclusion, according to the information obtained from the literature review, common problems are encountered in the internship process carried out in Vocational and Technical Anatolian High Schools in secondary education. These are briefly: students not doing their internships in their own departments, the problem of finding an internship place, student-induced incompatibility problems, students not knowing enough about the rights given to them by laws and regulations, lack of cooperation between school and sector, insufficiency of coordinator teacher / vice principal, inadequate vocational guidance, lack of motivation. However, the existing literature does not sufficiently explore the underlying causes of these problems, particularly the impact of students' internship experiences on their professional competencies, from a qualitative perspective. This study aims to address this gap in the literature by conducting an in-depth analysis of the internship experiences of civil aviation department students and providing concrete recommendations on how to improve these experiences at both individual and sectoral levels.

3. Methodology

This section includes information on the research model, study group, data collection method, data collection and data analysis.

3.1. Research Design

Qualitative research method was used in this study. Qualitative research is more oriented towards a social or human problem and also tries to explore the meanings attributed by individuals or groups (Creswell, 2017). Qualitative research is a research method in which qualitative data collection tools such as observation, interview, and document analysis are preferred, and perceptions and events are approached realistically and holistically in a natural environment (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). The research problem focuses on the difficulties experienced by civil aviation students during the internship process by addressing a current problem. Qualitative research method was preferred in order to determine the reasons for this situation in depth.

This study was designed in the case study model, one of the qualitative research designs. According to Yıldırım and Şimşek (2018), case study aims to draw conclusions about a specific situation with a quantitative or qualitative approach. The most basic feature of qualitative case study is to investigate the factors such as environment, individuals, events, processes, etc. related to a situation in a holistic manner and to reveal the situation in depth.

3.2. Study Group

Criterion sampling method, which is one of the purposeful sampling methods, was used to determine whether there are similarities or differences between the theoretical and practical training of vocational high school students in order to evaluate their educational experiences during the internship process. Purposive sampling method can be defined as a strategy in which certain environments, people or events are selected purposively, taking into account the important information they can contribute (Maxwell, 2008). According to Patton (1987), what strengthens this method is that it is useful in selecting participants/persons with sufficient information to create depth in the research.

The criteria sought for the participants in this study were as follows: Studying civil aviation in a vocational high school, doing an internship in the aviation sector, residing in Istanbul, and being in the Anatolian vocational program as a program type. Participants were students studying in public schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education Vocational and Technical Anatolian High Schools in Avcılar district of Istanbul province. All of the participants were civil aviation students in the transportation branch. The reason for the participants being in the same region and in the same branch is that their experiences and ideas are to be addressed in a common context in accordance with the case analysis.

Figure 1: Mehmet Emin Horoz Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School civil aviation department trainee student distribution

Figure1. above shows the distribution of the places where 12th grade civil aviation students studying at the school do their internships. In this distribution, only the students who did internship in the aviation sector are included. Out of a total of 60 students, only 34 students are doing internships in the aviation sector, while the remaining 26 students are doing internships in logistics companies and other companies.

According to Creswell (2013), since study groups in case studies should ideally consist of three to 15 participants, the current study was conducted with 4 vocational high school students. Therefore, it is seen that this study group has a sufficient number of participants. The demographic information of the participants is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of intern students in the civil aviation department of Mehmet Emin Horoz Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School

	Department	Age	Internship Enterprise	Gender
S1	Civil Aviation	18	Turkish Technic	Male
S2	Civil Aviation	18	THY DO & CO	Female
S3	Civil Aviation	18	General Directorate of State Airports Authority	Male
S4	Civil Aviation	18	THY DO & CO	Male

3.3. Data Collection Tools

The semi-structured interview form creates some flexibility by including open-ended questions and producing semi-structured interviews. These allow the interviewer to capture unexpected problems and information (Barbour & Schostak, 2005). The interview technique, which is frequently used in case studies, was used to collect data in the study (Johnson & Christensen, 2014). Therefore, in this case study, data were obtained through a semi-structured interview form.

The use of this technique was deemed appropriate as it allowed the participating students to explore their internship experiences in some depth, which helped the researchers to better understand their perspectives on the phenomena. In the study, the data were obtained through a semi-structured interview form in order to see the experiences of vocational high school students in the internship process. Repetition of the questions answered according to the semi-structured flow will be prevented. While preparing the semi-structured interview form, the questions in the domestic and foreign sources discussed in the literature review and the questions developed by the researcher within the scope of this study were taken into consideration.

The interview form was prepared based on the findings and recommendations derived from previous studies on civil aviation education and internship processes in vocational high schools (e.g., Somuncu, 2019; Yavaş et al., 2021; Numanoğlu et al., 2018). This form aimed to understand students' experiences and challenges during their internship processes and was finalized through revisions made in light of the critiques and suggestions of field experts. While the interview form started with a total of 9 questions, it was simplified and reduced to 4 questions as a result of pilot interviews. The questions were prepared in line with the conceptual framework of the research. The interview questions aimed to reveal what the participants experienced during the internship process and how these experiences were reflected in their lives. Pilot interviews were conducted with a volunteer participant to increase the reliability and validity of the questions in the interview form. In these pilot interviews, the incomprehensible and incomplete points that the participant in question saw in the questions were reconsidered and arrangements were made in the interview form. The researchers have evaluated the new adjustments to the questions and have initiated interviews with the participants. In this respect, the questions were made simpler, clearer and more suitable for the case study. In this context, the main outlines of the interview questions have been determined as follows:

1. What were your motivations for choosing the field of civil aviation?
2. How did the vocational courses you completed during high school enhance your internship experience?
3. In what ways did your internship experiences influence your professional competencies in the field?
4. Reflecting on the entire internship process, what challenges did you encounter, and what changes would you propose to improve the experience?

Afterwards, interviews were conducted with semi-structured interview questions.

3.4. Data Collection

The data collection process was carried out over a two-month period starting from May 2023 in the 2022-2023 academic year. During the data collection process, students were first contacted by phone and informed about the purpose of the study. In addition, the participants were informed that their personal information would not be disclosed during and after the study and would remain confidential. Then, a voluntary participation form was sent to each participant. Decisions were made about the place and time of the interviews with the students who decided to participate in the study. Interviews were conducted one-on-one by visiting the students' schools or through telephone interviews. During the interviews, audio recordings were made with the knowledge and consent of each participant. After each interview, the audio recording was transcribed by the researcher, then the participant was contacted for confirmation and asked if there was any misunderstanding of the transcribed interview data and if they wanted any topics to be added or removed.

The interviews with the participants were repeated twice in a two-month period and completed with dialogs lasting between 45 and 60 minutes. During the interviews, no one other than the participant and the researcher was present in the room. The principle of confidentiality was adhered to.

3.5. Data Analysis

In this study, content analysis technique, one of the qualitative data analysis techniques, was used to analyze the data. This method was applied to identify the themes that can best describe the difficulties and obstacles faced by vocational high school students according to their experiences in the internship process. Content analysis provides in-depth analysis of the collected data and reveals themes or dimensions that were not previously evident (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). Yıldırım and Şimşek (2018) stated that the main purpose of content analysis is to reach concepts and relationships that can adequately explain the collected data and that four stages should be followed during the analysis; these are coding the data, finding themes, organizing codes and themes, describing and interpreting the findings. In parallel to this, the steps suggested by Smith and Osborn (2015) and Moustakas (1994) for analyzing interview data were used in the content analysis of the data obtained.

1. Data Review: Interview recordings are reviewed, and significant terminologies are identified and transcribed.
2. Coding: Data are coded based on the responses to the questions, and themes are identified.
3. Thematic Analysis: Identified themes are reviewed, differences and similarities are analyzed, and adjustments are made.
4. Grouping: Similar themes are grouped, overarching themes are created, and all data are reviewed to finalize the coding process.

In the context of these methods, the audio-recorded interviews were transcribed. The data obtained in qualitative research are usually in formats such as audio recording or text. These data need to be digitized and made understandable for the reader. In this study, the interviews obtained from the students were transferred to Microsoft Office Word program as text. In the next stage, the answers given by all students were read and the framework of the answers was noted. Basic groups (themes) and subgroups (codes) were formed within the framework of the notes taken. The interview responses were re-read within the framework of these themes and codes, and it was noted which teacher responded within which theme and code. In the next stage, the number of responses for each code was presented in a table. After the presentation of the tables, sample quotations were made from the teachers' responses for each code. In the quotations, the expressions directly related to the codes are indicated in bold.

In the study, the participant students were coded as S1, S2, S3, S4. The analysis and interpretation of the data obtained from the participants are given in the findings and interpretations section.

4. Results and Discussion

In this part of the study, the findings and interpretations of vocational high school students' experiences and thoughts on the internship process are presented. The results that emerged within the scope of the 6 basic questions in the interview form were analyzed in detail by coding under themes. As a result of the content

analysis conducted for this purpose, 1) Findings related to the student, 2) Findings related to education and training program, 3) Under 3 main themes, 9 sub-themes and 28 codes were reached under 3 main themes as findings related to internship experience. This section provides a detailed explanation of the themes. Each theme was written with direct quotations in order to reveal the problems in the experiences of vocational high school students in the internship process.

4.1. Findings Related to the Student

When Table 2. is examined, the distribution of the views of the students participating in the research on what the profession and internship mean based on their self-expression consists of 3 sub-themes and 10 codes.

Table 2: Distribution of findings related to the student

Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
Findings about the student	Vocational orientation	Conscious choice
		Obligation
		Subsequent orientation
	Need for guidance	Need for vocational guidance
		Academic guidance needs
		Positive effect on motivation related to the profession
Communication	Professional communication	
	Self-expression	
	Excitement	
	Self-confidence	
Total		10 Codes

In the findings related to the students, it was seen that they mentioned their problems about career orientation, guidance needs and communication needs. Under these three main headings, it is seen that they feel deficiency in career preference, guidance needs and communication issues.

Vocational orientation: Vocational orientation emerges as a critical theme in understanding how internship experiences influence students’ career goals. The statements of S1 clearly highlight the impact of internships on vocational orientation. S1 noted, *“When I observed the shift-based working system during my internship at Turkish Technic, I realized that becoming an aircraft technician or engineer would be more suitable for me,”* indicating how the internship reshaped their career aspirations. This observation aligns with Yavaş et al. (2021), who emphasized that internships play a crucial role in shaping students' career goals and clarifying their professional preferences.

Similarly, S2 stated that they entered the field of civil aviation with the goal of becoming a pilot. However, the mismatch between the internship field and the academic program negatively impacted their motivation. S2 remarked, *“I continued with the internship because the company was a large firm, which was important for my CV,”* illustrating the mismatch between internship expectations and actual experiences, as highlighted by Leslie and Richardson (2000). This provides valuable insights into the long-term effects of internships on students’ career planning.

Need for guidance and support: The need for guidance plays a critical role in resolving the challenges students encounter during their internship experiences. However, this need is not always adequately met. For example, S4, who aspired to pursue a career in logistics, was redirected to civil aviation due to limited available placements. S4 stated, *“I didn’t research this field much at first, but I don’t regret choosing it,”* demonstrating how a lack of guidance influenced their career decisions. Konate (2022) also emphasized that students who do not make informed career choices face greater challenges during their internships and require more guidance.

The role of coordinating teachers also emerges as a significant factor in this context. S1 highlighted the positive impact of guidance by stating, *“My coordinating teacher directed me to intern at the best company,”* whereas S4 pointed out deficiencies in the process, noting, *“We had difficulty reaching our coordinating teacher.”* This aligns with findings by Gülsoy (2007), who emphasized that coordinating teachers should closely monitor students' needs.

Communication: Internships are seen as opportunities for students to develop their communication and social skills. S1 expressed, *“I learned how to address people and behave in the workplace,”* highlighting the

contributions of internships to social skills. Similarly, S4 stated, “*I learned teamwork, and my communication skills improved,*” demonstrating the impact of workplace experiences on personal development. Chen et al. (2021) support this view, noting that interns develop professional relationships, crisis management skills, and emotional intelligence in the workplace.

However, some students reported negative attitudes from staff toward interns. S1 shared, “*Being perceived as just an intern is exhausting; people don’t take us seriously,*” illustrating this challenge. Çiçek (2021) emphasized that such negative experiences reduce students’ motivation and highlighted the need for greater support in the workplace.

These findings illustrate how internships shape students' vocational orientation, communication skills, and guidance needs. However, improvements are needed in areas such as addressing guidance and support deficiencies and enhancing staff attitudes toward interns. A stronger guidance system and increased support for students in their internship environments can significantly enhance their professional development and motivation.

4.2. Findings related to the education and training program

When Table 3. is examined, the distribution of the opinions of the students participating in the research on the education and training system consists of 3 sub-themes and 8 codes.

Table 3: Distribution of findings related to education and training program

Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
Findings Regarding the Education Curriculum	Lack of implementation	Learning by doing Professional incompetence
	The courses are theoretical	Vocational courses are not useful in internship Incompatibility of the content of the courses
	Role of coordinator teacher	Lack of communication with the internship site Inadequate vocational guidance Ineffective coordinator activities Difficulty finding an internship place
Total		8 Codes

In the distribution of the findings related to the education-training program, the lack of practice, the theoretical nature of the lessons and the place of the coordinator teacher were grouped under 3 sub-themes.

Lack of implementation: The misalignment between the theoretical courses provided in schools and the internship environment is one of the most common issues in vocational high school internship training. Participant S2 describes this situation as follows: “*The knowledge we learned at school could not be used in the internship environment. The subjects taught in class were completely unrelated to my internship tasks.*” This inconsistency leads to a loss of motivation among students during their internship process.

However, S3’s experience provides a different perspective: “*The aviation alphabet and de-icing procedures were information I used constantly during my internship. I had the opportunity to apply the theoretical knowledge I gained in practice.*” Such experiences demonstrate how the alignment of theoretical and practical training can significantly enhance students' professional skills. Similarly, Leslie and Richardson (2000) emphasize that when theoretical knowledge becomes applicable during internships, student motivation increases.

The courses are theoretical: The lack of balance between theoretical knowledge and practical application in internship training directly affects the quality of education. S1 articulates this issue as follows: “*The internship was a great opportunity to see how the information we learned on paper is applied in the workplace, but I couldn’t translate the aircraft knowledge I learned in high school into real-world applications.*” This highlights the need for updating theoretical content to align with industry requirements.

Somuncu (2019) reveals that the inadequacy of vocational course content leads to students experiencing a lack of practical knowledge in the field. In this context, internship environments should be structured to provide students with opportunities to apply their theoretical knowledge in practice.

Role of the coordinating teacher: The guidance skills of coordinating teachers play a crucial role in ensuring that students maximize the benefits of their internship experiences. S1 supports this with the following statement: “*The coordinating teacher is the person who provided me with vocational training and matched me*

with the most suitable company.” This underscores the role of coordinating teachers in helping students establish industry connections and define their professional goals.

However, the need for coordinating teachers to be more active in the field is also emphasized. S1’s expectation, “I would have liked the coordinating teacher to physically see the work I was doing at the airport,” highlights the importance of on-site supervision in addressing the gaps between theoretical and practical training. Similar findings presented by Çiçek (2021) in the literature support this call. Additionally, Somuncu (2019) points out that infrastructure deficiencies in newly established civil aviation programs increase the need for coordinating teacher guidance.

4.3. Findings related to internship experience

When Table 4. is examined, the distribution of the opinions of the students participating in the study about the internship experience consists of 3 sub-themes and 10 codes.

Table 4: Distribution of findings related to internship experience

Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
Findings about the internship experience	Incompatibility of the internship with the curriculum	Not being employed in field-related work at the work place Off-branch work Job rotation
	Working hours	Early working hours Transportation difficulties Distance to the internship site Excessive workload
	Human relations	Not having the same rights as the staff at the workplace Not having enough time for friends, family and self due to school and internship How to approach other people
Total		10 Codes

The findings related to the internship experience consist of 3 sub-themes: incompatibility of the internship with the curriculum, working hours, and human relations.

Incompatibility of the internship with the curriculum: S4 described their internship experience as follows: “The place where I interned was more focused on culinary activities, so I didn’t learn anything related to aviation.” This statement clearly highlights the misalignment between the student’s internship placement and their field of study. Leslie and Richardson (2000) noted that such mismatches negatively affect students’ professional development and career aspirations. Similarly, Özgül (1995) emphasized that working outside one’s area of expertise increases vocational training costs and hinders the effective utilization of human resources.

S2 stated, “There was no connection between what I learned in classes last year and the tasks I performed during my internship. This made things very difficult for me and decreased my motivation.” Such circumstances are key factors preventing students from benefiting from their internship experiences.

This misalignment between curricula and internship placements disrupts students’ processes of acquiring professional competencies. Çiçek (2021) emphasized that a compatible internship environment plays a critical role in both applying theoretical knowledge in practice and enhancing professional motivation. Furthermore, MEB (2019) suggested that strengthening education-business collaboration would be a significant step toward addressing these issues.

Working hours: S1 expressed the physical and mental exhaustion caused by early mornings and long working hours: “Waking up at the crack of dawn and going to work wore me out both physically and mentally.” Demirci (2007) noted that the working hours of vocational high school students negatively affect their social lives and academic performance.

S3 stated, “Long working hours distanced me from my studies and significantly impacted my social life. I had no energy left for anything when I came home.” This clearly illustrates the challenges students face in maintaining a work-life balance.

S2 remarked, *"When we missed the shuttle, it became impossible to get to work."* This demonstrates how transportation difficulties affect students' productivity during their internships. Pala (2016) identified such challenges as one of the main factors negatively impacting students' internship experiences.

Long working hours and inadequate transportation options are major barriers preventing students from gaining maximum benefit from their internships. Wang et al. (2019) stated that when work-life balance is not maintained, students exhibit lower workplace performance, which ultimately reduces long-term professional commitment. In contrast, the MEB's (2019) strategic plan recommends providing flexible working hours and transportation support tailored to students.

Human relations: S3 shared, *"The people I worked with treated me very well, and this made me feel more secure."* This experience underscores the critical role of positive interpersonal relationships in strengthening students' professional commitment, as highlighted by Chen et al. (2021).

S1 noted, *"When you first arrive, you are labeled as just an intern."* This statement reveals how workplace biases undermine students' motivation. Arslan (2020) observed that when students are not treated as equals in the workplace, their levels of professional satisfaction decline.

S4 stated, *"I had no mentor to support me at my workplace, so I had to figure out many things on my own. This both exhausted me and made me lose interest in the job."* This illustrates the negative impact of a lack of mentorship on interns.

The importance of human relations during internships is critical for students' professional development and adaptation to the working environment. Pınarlık et al. (2022) highlighted that a positive workplace culture and open communication provide significant advantages in developing students' professional skills. Additionally, they noted that mentorship programs are an effective method for enhancing interpersonal relationships.

5. Results and Discussion

Evaluations of the internship experiences of vocational high school students in civil aviation programs reveal significant shortcomings in current educational curricula and internship practices. Findings indicate that although the majority of students complete their internships within the aviation sector, their placements often fail to sufficiently align with their fields of study (Somuncu, 2019; Yavaş et al., 2021). This misalignment negatively impacts students' motivation for career choices and hinders the achievement of educational program objectives (Chen et al., 2021; Pınarlık et al., 2022).

The findings also suggest that internship challenges in the field of civil aviation largely overlap with those faced in other vocational high schools (Karataş, 2017; Çiçek, 2021). Key factors contributing to these issues include the limited support provided by the industry to high school students, the design of educational programs that fail to address sectoral needs, and the insufficient effectiveness of school-industry collaboration (MEB, 2019; Özgül, 1995). Additionally, technical and equipment deficiencies in internship organizations have hindered students from transitioning theoretical knowledge into practical experience. These shortcomings constitute major barriers to students' development of professional knowledge and skills.

To make internship processes more effective and efficient, strong collaboration must be established between students, coordinating teachers, business representatives, and parents (Numanoğlu et al., 2018; T.C. MEB, 2014). For example, greater educational support from business representatives for intern students can play a crucial role in enhancing their professional competencies. Moreover, implementing mentorship programs can help students feel more comfortable in workplace environments.

The attitude of workplace personnel toward intern students is also a critical factor directly influencing students' professional motivation and commitment (Chen et al., 2021). Internship experiences shape students' professional orientation and play an essential role in determining their career goals. Therefore, creating a positive working environment for interns is of critical importance to maximize their professional experiences. For instance, active guidance and integration of interns into work processes by employees can increase students' commitment to the job. Furthermore, expanding educational opportunities that allow theoretical knowledge to

be reinforced practically and ensuring effective guidance within the workplace are essential (Leslie & Richardson, 2000).

To further support the professional development of intern students, rotational internship systems can be implemented in businesses. Such a system can enable students to gain experience in different departments and diversify their skills. This approach is particularly valuable in a field like aviation, where technical knowledge and skills are paramount, as it helps students better determine their career goals. Additionally, providing comprehensive training on occupational health and safety to interns can enhance both their safety and professional qualifications.

Finally, restructuring educational programs to align with sectoral needs can contribute to the professional success of intern students. Educational programs should aim to balance the delivery of both theoretical and practical knowledge. In this regard, involving industry representatives in the design of educational programs can help ensure that curricula are better aligned with sectoral expectations. Furthermore, providing students with feedback at the end of the internship process can help them understand their strengths and areas for improvement. Such a feedback mechanism can support students in making more informed decisions in their career journeys.

6. Suggestions

According to the information obtained during the research process, the internship places of the students who will do internship should be found by the school. While choosing the internship places, they should be suitable for the curriculum and should be places where students can have the opportunity to apply the theoretical knowledge they have learned at school in their internship places. Coordinator teachers who go to internship supervision should regularly supervise interns and be in contact with students. In addition, teaching supervisors in the workplaces should be selected among experienced and willing personnel and their training should be provided continuously. Occupational health and safety measures at internship sites should be implemented taking into account the age group of the intern students.

Opportunities such as in-service training should be provided to improve the knowledge and skills of internship students during the internship process. Necessary measures should be taken for the student to develop skills in different units at the internship site. Necessary advice should be given to students about communication with other staff, supervisors and friends at the internship site. At the end of the internship period, students should be given realistic information about their professional career. Students should be informed about the company and undergo in-service training before going to the internship. It is also recommended that coordinating teachers stay in regular contact with company officials. Finally, coordinating teachers who cannot enter the company due to some security measures at the airport should communicate more closely with the company officials to ensure supervision.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

This research was conducted in accordance with the principles of scientific research and publication ethics.

References

- Arslan, S. (2020). *Mesleki ve teknik liselerde bilişim teknolojileri alanı stajlarının değerlendirilmesi (İstanbul Ataşehir ilçesi örneği)* [Yüksek lisans]. Maltepe Üniversitesi Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü.
- Barbour, R. S. & Schostak, J. (2005). Interviewing and focus groups. B. Somekh and C. Lewin (Eds.), *Research methods in the social sciences* (p. 41-49). Sage Publications.
- Bozak, A. (2019). *Meslek lisesi bilişim teknolojileri alanı öğrencilerinin işletmelerde beceri eğitiminde karşılaştıkları sorunlar ve çözüm önerileri (Denizli ili örneği)* [Yüksek lisans]. Pamukkale Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü.

- Chen, B. T., Lu, C.Y., Chang, M. C. & Lin, C. Y. J. (2021). Motives for internships-airline ground crew as an example. *Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism*, 21(1), 19-42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15313220.2020.1768620>
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). Nitel araştırma yöntemleri beş yaklaşıma göre nitel araştırma ve araştırma deseni. M. Bütün & S. B. Demir (Eds.), *Qualitative research methods*. Siyasal Kitabevi.
- Creswell, J. W. (2017). Nitel Yöntemler. Selçuk Beşir Demir (Eds.), *Araştırma deseni nitel, nicel ve karma yöntem araştırmaları*. Eğiten Kitap.
- Çiçek, M. (2021). *İstanbul'da açılış eğitimi alan öğrencilerin mesleğe yönelik tutumlarının kariyer niyetlerine etkisi* [Yüksek lisans]. Mersin Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Demirci, M. S. (2007). Ticaret meslek liselerinde staj yapan öğrencilerin işletmelerde beceri eğitiminde karşılaştıkları sorunlar ve çözüm yolları [Yüksek lisans]. Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Gülsoy, B. Ş. (2007). Endüstri meslek lisesi elektrik-elektronik bölümünde öğrenim gören öğrencilerin işletmede uygulanan mesleki eğitim (staj) çalışmasının değerlendirilmesi [Yüksek lisans]. Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Johnson, B. & Christensen, L. (2014). *Eğitim Araştırmaları (4. Baskıdan Çeviri)*. Eğiten Kitap.
- Karataş, B. (2017). *İşletmelerde staj yapan mesleki ve teknik Anadolu lisesi öğrencilerinin sorunlarına ilişkin öğrenci görüşleri* [Yüksek lisans]. Sakarya Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü
- Konate, A. D. (2022). Meslek lisesi öğrencilerinin 21. yy becerileri ve umut düzeylerinin kariyer karar verme güçlüğü ile ilişkisinin incelenmesi [Yüksek lisans]. Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Leslie, D. & Richardson, A. (2000). Tourism and cooperative education in UK undergraduate courses. *Tourism Management*, 21(5), 489-498. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177\(99\)00103-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177(99)00103-X)
- Maxwell, J. (2008). Designing a qualitative study. *Qualitative Research*. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781483348858.n7>
- MEB. (2014). *Türkiye mesleki ve teknik eğitim strateji belgesi ve eylem planı 2014-2018*. http://mtegm.meb.gov.tr/meb_iys_dosyalar/2016_07/29122004_mte_stareji_belgesi_20_14_2018_1.pdf
- MEB. (2019). *Koordinatör öğretmen el kitabı*. http://mtegm.meb.gov.tr/meb_iys_dosyalar/2019_11/26115454_KOORDYNATOR_OYRETMEN_EL_KYTABI.pdf
- Moustakas, C. (1994). *Phenomenological research methods*. Sage publications.
- Numanoğlu, K. V., Suna, E., Tanberkan, H., Eroğlu, E., Altun, Ü., Demircan, A., Bakırkaya, E., & Seçen, A. (2018). *Meslekî ve teknik ortaöğretimde kurumsal dış değerlendirme raporu*. http://mtegm.meb.gov.tr/meb_iys_dosyalar/2018_12/19140043_29103339_mesleki_ve_teknik_ortaogretimde_kurumsal_dis_degerlendirme_raporu_web_29kasim.pdf
- Örnek, Ü. (2021). *İş yeri beceri eğitimi bağlamında ortaöğretim kurumları ulaştırma hizmetleri alanı lojistik dalı öğrencilerinin verimlilikleri ve karşılaşılan sorunlar üzerine bir uygulama* [Yüksek lisans]. Tarsus Üniversitesi Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü.
- Özgül, N. (1995). *İşletmelerde staj yapan meslek lisesi öğrencilerine staj yaptıkları kurumların mesleki etkilerinin belirlenmesine yönelik bir araştırma* [Yüksek lisans]. İstanbul Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Pala, H. (2016). Meslek lisesi öğrencilerinin uygulama staj algılarının çeşitli demografik değişkenler açısından incelenmesi [Yüksek lisans]. Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Patton, M. Q. (1987). *How to use qualitative methods in evaluation* (Sayı 4). Sage Publications
- Paul, B. & Gill, M. (1993). Hospitality management students' image of the hospitality industry. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 5(5), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596119310046961>
- Pınarlık, G., Yıldırım, G., Yıldırım, A., & Saraç, R. (2022). Sivil havacılık meslek yüksekokulu, uçak teknolojisi programı stajları ve işyerlerinin beklentileri üzerine bir araştırma. *Türkiye Mesleki ve Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*. <https://doi.org/10.46236/jvosst.1218160>
- Sarı, H. (2007). *Ortaöğretim düzeyinde mesleki turizm eğitimi alan öğrencilerin staj sürecine adaptasyonu üzerine bir araştırma* [Yüksek lisans]. Gazi Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri.
- Smith, J. A. & Osborn, M. (2015). Interpretative phenomenological analysis as a useful methodology for research on the lived experience of pain. *British Journal of Pain*, 9(1), 41-42. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2049463714541642>

- Somuncu, A. (2019). Mesleki ve teknik liselerde yeni oluşturulan sivil havacılık yer hizmetleri alan eğitiminin değerlendirilmesi. *Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi Turizm Fakültesi Dergisi*, 22(1), 81-108. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/ahbvtfd/issue/46506/583981>
- Wang, X., Li, C., Fan, W., & Liu, X. (2019). A Survey on the Internship Status of Students Majoring in Civil Aviation-Take Sanya Aviation and Tourism College as an Example (ss. 399-410). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-35095-6_43
- Yavaş, V., Macit, A., & Yeşilay, R.B. (2021). A study on civil aviation students' evaluation of their internship experiences. *Yükseköğretim Dergisi*, 11(21), 331-343. <https://doi.org/10.2399/yod.20.521417>
- Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2018). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri* (11. bs). Seçkin Yayıncılık.
- Yılmaz, N. (2021). *Meslek liselerinin muhasebe bölümlerinde verilen eğitimin piyasa ihtiyaçlarına uygunluğunun değerlendirilmesi İstanbul ilinde meslek liseleri üzerinde bir uygulama* [Yüksek lisans]. İstanbul Aydın Üniversitesi Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü.

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence**.

Copyright © 2024 Research in Aviation Management <http://ramjournal.org>